

Zeros of Quantum Spatial Probability Density

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 1, 2023

Quantum spatial probability is given by $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)=\sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction. If one knows about a particle's location through $W^*(x)W(x)$ then momentum is uncertain. On the other hand, $a^*(p)a(p)$ is the probability for a particle to have a specific p free particle momentum. In that case, there is no knowledge of the location of the particle.

In (1) it is argued that for an infinite potential one dimensional box, the wavefunction is $\sin(n\pi x/L)$ and so $W(x)W(x)$ may have zero values within the box. It is stated that this is unphysical as there is no reason a particle cannot be at such an x point. (The resolution in (1) is to consider a linear superposition of energy eigenfunctions based on certain rules.)

In this note, we consider that $a(p)$ values suggest there are probabilities for a particle to have a constant p momentum. This momentum means the particle may move through all points x because even in the quantum free particle case $\exp(ipx)$, a two dimensional dynamical probability implies: $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$. Thus a measurement of a p value (i.e. a constant value) even with no known corresponding x value suggests the particle may be anywhere in the system, even at zero points of the wavefunction. The bound wavefunction is real and so is an average which removes the dynamism of the system i.e. the two A particle does not exist in all p states at once. The zeros of $W(x)$ appear only because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ interfere revealing one dimension of the two dimensional probability. Thus we argue that $W(x)=0$ does not mean that a particle cannot be at x .

Classical Versus Quantum Physics

Classical physics describes a particle as $x(t)$ so given t , one knows x and all derivatives dx/dt , d^2x/dt^2 etc. A derivative, however, requires information about the particle at x and $x+\delta$ so one really does not know about that particle's derivatives at x unless δ shrinks to 0, as it does in calculus. In the real world, however, this idea of localizing a particle to a point may be an idealization. In particular, quantum mechanics describes a free particle by $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. for a constant p there is a two dimensional dynamic probability $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. The particle is localized not to a point, but to a region $\approx \hbar/p$ (half a wavelength), but because it is moving, there is double uncertainty. Instead of being at x , it is within $\approx \hbar/p$ of x and at the same time the $x+\delta$ of classical physics means that this point is also uncertain. Thus one needs two probability distributions which are correlated in order to have $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ i.e. to have all x points treated in the same manner.

The fact that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ have zero values for certain x does not mean that the particle may not be at these x points. If $\cos(px)=0$ then $\sin(px) \neq 0$. The dynamical probability is critical in the interpretation of free particle motion, we argue.

Bound State Systems

A free particle moves with constant p and speed p/m (nonrelativistic) on average, but within a wavelength \hbar/p , there is uncertainty in the particle's position and its $x+\delta$ position as it

moves. In the case of a bound system with a potential $V(x)$, one takes a linear superposition of free particle wavefunctions i.e.

$$W(x) = \text{bound wavefunction (real)} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

$W(x)$ is an average, thus the particle is either in one p state or another. From quantum mechanics, however, one states that:

$$W^*(x)W(x) = \text{probability density in } x \text{ with no knowledge of a specific } p \quad ((2a))$$

$$\text{and } a^*(p)a(p) = \text{probability to have a free particle } p \text{ with no knowledge of the specific } x \quad ((2b))$$

It is possible that $W^*(x_a)W(x_a) = 0$ at certain x_a points. For example, in (1) it is stated that the wavefunction for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls is:

$$W(x) = C \sin(n \cdot 3.14/L) \text{ where } L \text{ is one dimensional box size} \quad ((3))$$

(1) states that it is unphysical to have 0 spatial probability at any x point within the box.

From ((2b)) one sees that even if one does not know the x value of a measured p , one knows from the existence of the free particle that it may be anywhere in the box. Thus one cannot state that a particle cannot be at x_a where $W(x_a) = 0$, we argue.

The resolution of this issue seems to be linked to the form $\exp(ipx)$. We noted that $\cos(px)$ may have a 0 value, but $\sin(px)$ does not for the same x_a . Thus the particle is not excluded from the point x_a .

In the case of a bound state one has a real wavefunction which means that the two dimensional dynamism of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ has been removed and replaced with the static $\cos(px)$ type piece (even parity) through the interference of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ with $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ with $a(p) = a(-p)$. Thus $W(x)$ does not represent the full dynamics of a bound system. It does, however, give the height and width of the various peaks/troughs which appear in the system and this is important physical information. Thus $W(x_a) = 0$ only means that a one dimensional average of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ s has a zero value and not that a particle cannot be at x_a .

High Energy Level Limit

To further see issues with the limited dynamism in $W(x)$, one may consider the high energy limit. For low energy, interference of various $\exp(ipx)$ s occurs because most \hbar/p wavelengths are of the order of the system length. Probabilistically one may not follow the particle using $x(t)$ within a half wavelength and if the wavelength is large, one does not know if the particle has reflected or changed to another p , or is somewhere within its own half wavelength etc. As the energy level becomes very high, the peaks/troughs of $W(x)$ become very narrow and for any tiny Δx (small compared to L the system length) one has a peak mimicking $\cos(p_{rms} \text{ ave } x)$. This, however, is not the full dynamics of the problem because $p_{rms} \text{ ave}$ i.e. the classical p would correspond to a quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)$ which has two dimensions.

Thus we argue that the wavefunction does not contain the full dynamism of the problem. For high energy levels, the particle moves to the right and then to the left, but the wavefunction is an average which has time removed and includes p and $-p$ together for any energy level which seems to be unphysical, but reveals the peak/trough structure.

Interpretation of the Wavefunction

If the wavefunction does not contain the full dynamics of a particle, what use does it serve? One may note that a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ contains two dimensions of probability $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ because it is dynamic. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ so one may ask: Why should one be concerned with the form $\cos(px)$? This form, however, is physical in terms of impulse hits which occur at small lengths such as with a two slit apparatus with the length between slits of the order of \hbar/p . Thus $\cos(px)$, which only represents one dimension, is still important as it shows the granularity present. Similarly for a bound system, $W(x)$ does not contain the full dynamism, but shows the type of granularity present in an average system which is important at low energy. $W(x)W(x)$ represents a kind of averaged spatial probability with dynamism removed so we argue that one must be careful about stating that a particle cannot be found at x_a if $W(x_a)=0$. A particle is measured through an impulse hit and this is based on a free particle which may be at any x point, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ representing a free particle has two dimensions of probability, one for x which classical is a point, but quantum mechanically is a distribution $\cos(px)$ and another for $x+\delta$ i.e. $\sin(px)$ which is needed to describe dynamism in the problem.

$\cos(px)$ by itself shows the granular probability which is important while $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ shows that the particle may be at any x point with the same probability. One does not conclude that because $\cos(p x_a)=0$ the free particle cannot be at x_a .

In (1) it is argued that for a single particle in a one dimensional infinite potential well, $W(x)=C \sin(n \cdot 3.14/L)$ which may be 0 inside the well and that this is unphysical. We argue that $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ where $\exp(ipx)$ represents a free particle and $a(p)a(p)$ the probability to have p with no information about the precise x point. If one measures a p then it may be at any x point thus $W(x_a)=0$ cannot mean that the particle may not be found at x_a .

$W(x)$ is a superposition of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ values and so for $a(p)=a(-p)$ dynamism of motion is removed, but this is critical information. What $W(x)$ shows is the new granularity i.e. $\cos(px) \rightarrow W(x)$. Thus one may see the structure of the spatial probability granularity, but $W(x_a)$ does not mean that a particle cannot be at x_a , we argue.

The authors of (1) try to resolve the probability issue by considering the particle to be in a superposition of energy eigenstate.

References

1. Purwanto, A. et al Inconsistency of Probability Density in Quantum Mechanics and its Solution (Open Journal of Microphysics Article ID 19226
[DOI:10.4236/ojm.2012.22002](https://doi.org/10.4236/ojm.2012.22002))
https://www.scirp.org/html/1-1220020_19226.htm